

1 Optical Configuration (Rev. 1)

The optical configuration described in the GAIA proposal, and subsequently studied by Loiseau & Shaklan (ESA SP-379, p. 241, and Applied Optics) and by Ceconi & Lattanzi (ESA SP-379, p. 251), had a relatively short focal length of $F \sim 12$ m compatible with the use of a modulating grid. More recent studies of possible optical configurations have aimed at a much longer focal length, as required by direct fringe detection. This section gives a short description of three such configurations, which could be taken as examples of the many possible variations of similar systems. A comparative summary is provided of the configurations in terms of the basic optical parameters and relative astrometric precision, illustrating some of the factors influencing the final accuracy.

All three configurations seem capable of producing diffraction-limited performance at least over the field of view indicated in each case, i.e. with (monochromatic) visibilities > 0.9 . The accuracy (σ) scales roughly as the inverse of the mean visibility in the field, and this is not taken into account in the comparison.

Another factor not yet considered is geometrical distortion. The general requirement is that, across a single CCD chip, the deviation from the best-fitting constant-scale representation of that chip should not exceed a certain fraction of the fringe period (TBC).

1.1 Example 1: AS Configuration

This configuration was taken from the technical note SE/TNI 127/97 (10 March 1997), but with baseline, pupil diameter and field diameter modified according to Lattanzi (23 May 1997). It is a three-mirror telescope with main optical parameters as in Table 1. It can be described as a Cassegrain telescope (M1+M2) with a third mirror (M3) re-imaging the intermediate focal surface (IF) and compensating its curvature. The exit pupil (P1) is located between M3 and the final focal plane (FF). The equivalent focal length is 30 m. Since the focal plane optically occupies a position near the intermediate focus, one or more diagonal mirrors must be inserted after the intermediate focus in order to shift the physical focus out of the incoming beam.

Table 1. Approximate optical parameters of the AS configuration.

Element	Position (m)	Radius of curvature (m)	Conicity	Diameter (m)
P0	3.200			3.150
M1	3.400	-7.696	+	3.150
M2	0.000	-1.061	-	0.420
F1	2.900			0.350
M3	4.000	-1.202	+	0.760
P1	3.385			0.075
FF	2.675	∞	-	0.420

1.2 Example 2: OATo Configuration

This configuration (Lattanzi, 23 May 1997) is somewhat similar to the original GAIA design, but with one more mirror allowing better compensation of aberrations and a longer focal length. It does not require folding of the light beam, and is therefore very compact, but baffling may be a critical problem. The main optical parameters are shown in Table 2. There is no intermediate focus and the exit pupil is virtual, i.e. located behind the final focal plane. The equivalent focal length is 25 m. Both M3 and M4 are aspheric.

Table 2. Approximate optical parameters of the OATo configuration.

Element	Position (m)	Radius of curvature (m)	Conicity	Diameter (m)
P0	3.335			2.950
M1	3.435	-15.195	+	2.950
M2	0.000	-15.522	-	TBD
M3	3.340	+33.243	+	TBD
M4	0.503	-1305.6		TBD
FF	3.313	∞	-	0.330

1.3 Example 3: 95B Configuration

This configuration was taken from a note by Høg (28 April 1997, #4). The primary mirror (M1) forms an intermediate focus (F1) which is re-imaged by an inverted Schmidt telescope (mirror M2 and corrector plate C) onto the final focal plane (FF). A field lens (L) at the intermediate focus is required to eliminate field curvature (and to image the entrance pupil on the Schmidt corrector?). An additional correcting element (C2) may be placed between the Schmidt corrector and the focal plane. It is possible to eliminate all five Seidel aberrations by variation of the five elements M1, L, M2, C and C2. To accommodate the Schmidt corrector away from the incoming beam, a diagonal mirror is placed near the intermediate focus. The slowly converging beam from the Schmidt system is folded by additional mirrors to restrict the overall size. The effective focal length is 60 m.

The configuration as described by Høg uses a beam combiner located approximately 3 m in front of the primary mirror. The entrance pupil (P0) is located at the beam combiner. The exit pupil (P1) falls between the field lens and the corrector plate and is thus accessible.

Table 3. Approximate optical parameters of the 95B configuration.

Element	Position (m)	Radius of curvature (m)	Conicity	Diameter (m)
P0	1.500			2.000
M1	4.559	-7.600	<i>TBD</i>	2.000
F1 = L	0.759			0.047
M2	0.000	+1.428	<i>TBD</i>	0.440
P1	1.500			0.450
C	1.428			0.450
FF	12.00	∞	—	0.520

1.4 A Comparative Summary

In a first approximation the astrometric performance only depends on certain key optical parameters, such as the shape and size of the pupil, the effective focal length, and the available field of view. Table 4 gives a comparative summary of the three configurations described above in terms of such key parameters, and in terms of the astrometric precision for direct fringe detection (without fringe dispersion) estimated according to Appendix TBD. Following the studies from which the configurations were adopted, the pixel size in the scanning direction was assumed to be $2.4 \mu\text{m}$ for the AS and AOTo configurations, and $5 \mu\text{m}$ for the 95B configuration. For the comparison, a flat response (of $TQ = 0.5$) was assumed over a wavelength region of 400 to 700 nm. Two interferometers were assumed, and a field utilization of 70 per cent (fraction of focal surface covered by CCD's).

The different astrometric precision for the three configurations depends on several factors, such as differences in detector solid angle, in the frequency of fringe sampling, and so on. Table 5 is an attempt to 'explain' the total factor on σ_a in terms of the key parameters. The precision (σ) is basically assumed to scale as B^{-1} , $A^{-1/2}$, and $\Omega^{-1/2}$, other things being equal; however, this is strongly modified by other factors such as the fringe sampling (ratio of pixel width to fringe period) and the pupil geometry (in particular the ratio B/D), both of which also depend on B . The dependence on fringe sampling was investigated by decreasing the pixel width to negligible values (and disregarding readout noise). The factor 'other' is what remains after the other factors have been taken into account. It is probably mainly related to the pupil geometry, as it appears correlated with B/D .

Table 4. A comparative summary of the three optical configurations. Pupil sizes are prefixed 'c' for circular shape (diameter given) and 's' for square shape (side length given).

Parameter	Designation	AS	OATo	95B	Unit
baseline	B	2.55	2.40	1.50	m
pupil size	D	c0.60	c0.60	s0.50	m
focal length	F	30.0	25.0	60.0	m
collecting area	A	0.57	0.57	0.50	m ²
fringe period (550 nm)	$F\lambda/B$	6.5	5.7	22.0	μm
pixel width	$F\Delta\xi$	2.4	2.4	5.0	μm
pixel height	$F\Delta\eta$	28.8	30.5	30.0	μm
angular field of view diameter	Φ	1.10	1.30	0.50	deg
linear field of view diameter	$F\Phi$	0.58	0.57	0.52	m
field utilization	q	0.7	0.7	0.7	—
detector solid angle	Ω	0.665	0.929	0.137	deg ²
mean time per star	τ	2280	3190	470	s
parallax precision ($V = 15$)	σ_a	8.2	8.1	20.7	μas
fringe sampling	$\Delta\xi B/\lambda$	0.37	0.42	0.23	—
pupil geometry	B/D	4.3	4.0	3.0	—

Table 5. A breakdown of the relative astrometric precision of the three configurations in terms of some key design features, taking the AS configuration as reference.

Feature	$\sigma(\text{OATo})/\sigma(\text{AS})$	$\sigma(95\text{B})/\sigma(\text{AS})$
baseline (B)	1.06	1.70
collecting area (A)	1.00	1.06
detector solid area (Ω)	0.85	2.20
fringe sampling ($\Delta\xi B/\lambda$)	1.12	0.77
other (B/D , etc)	0.98	0.82
total ratio	0.98	2.52

angle